

A security threat analysis for unified network orchestration across terrestrial and non-terrestrial resources

Matteo Battaglia,* Alessandro Cammarano,* Juan Manuel Villarreal D'Angelo,*
Jose Avila,† Maxime Compastie,† Hossein Rouzegar,†
*Osmium, Barcelona, Spain
†i2CAT Foundation, Barcelona, Spain
Emails: (mb, ac, jv)@osmium.solutions,
(jose.avila, maxime.compastie, hossein.rouzegar)@i2cat.net.

Abstract—The integration of non-terrestrial resources in telecommunication networks necessitates complementing the traditional orchestration paradigm to cope with the heterogeneity, the temporal access, the limited resources and the flexible topology of satellite resources. The design of a unified orchestrator to jointly supervise the lifecycle and connectivity of terrestrial and non-terrestrial resources is a viable option to maintain compatibility with industry standards while facilitating integration. However, the heightened vulnerable surface area creates additional opportunities for threat actors to exploit orchestration functionalities, posing an increased risk of security breaches. In this paper, we systematically review and justify the threat surface of a unified orchestrator by leveraging standard threat analysis methodologies. Our findings highlight that network architecture elements are not prominently exposed to the same threat whether they are located on the ground or satellite segment. From our findings we issue a set of design objectives to secure a unified orchestration framework.

Index Terms—network orchestration, non-terrestrial networks, threat analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

The sixth generation of mobile networks (6G) foresees satisfying the connectivity needs of new verticals such as the Internet of Sense, holographic communications and Internet of Things [1]. Those verticals are not only demanding on increasing traditional network capacity (i.e., bandwidth, latency) while limiting operational and capital expenditure, but they also solicit global and continuous connectivity to permit Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Low-Latency Communications (uRLLC), massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) to enable immersive and pervasive experiences [2], [3]. However, relying solely on Terrestrial Networks (TNs) may be insufficient to meet these objectives: while eMBB is challenged in remote areas with limited connectivity, uRLLC may be hampered by the complexity of legacy network infrastructures and mMTC completely disrupted by the absence of connectivity. To that end, researchers have directed their attention to Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) and considered their seamless integration in the backbones of the next generation of mobile networks.

One considered approach resides in the definition of a unified network orchestration process extending standardised

architecture to oversee both terrestrial and non-terrestrial resources, limiting the complexity of operation processes. However, the consequences of this integration remains to be fully understood, including from a security and trust perspective, as communications with non-terrestrial resources (e.g., satellital, unmanned aerial vehicles) are subjected to specific vulnerabilities exploited by threat actors. While prior work have covered the robustness of mobile network orchestration [4] and non-terrestrial resources [5] separately, a joint analysis of the vulnerability surface of the latter over the former has not yet been conducted, to the best of the authors knowledge.

In this paper, we identify and conduct an analysis of the security challenges associated with NTNs, focusing on the threats introduced by satellite communications and their impact on a unified network orchestrator covering both TNs and NTNs by extending ETSI NFV-MANO standards. To address these security threats and promote network robustness, we propose a set of security objectives to be accounted into the design of the unified orchestrator.

This paper is organised as follows: Section II revises the reference architecture provided by ETSI for virtualised network, and its extension to unified orchestration, detailing the functioning of the different system components. Section III presents the tailoring of the NFV architecture for NTNs. Section IV presents the STRIDE methodology, adopted to conduct the threat assessment. This methodology is leveraged in Section V to identify the threats targeting a unified network orchestrator. Sections VI issues the several security objectives to mitigate the identified threats. Section VII concludes the paper and discusses future work.

II. ETSI NFV ARCHITECTURAL FRAMEWORK

Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV) is a network architecture concept aiming at decoupling network functions from hardware, and running them as software-based instances on a virtualised infrastructure. This enhances network agility, scalability, and cost-effectiveness by leveraging standard IT virtualisation techniques.

According to the ETSI reference model [6], the architecture of NFV is composed of three main functional blocks (Fig. 1):

Fig. 1. ETSI NFV architectural framework

NFV Infrastructure (NFVI): the totality of all hardware and software components which build up the environment in which the VNFs are deployed, managed and executed. It can span across several locations, known as NFVI-PoPs (Points of Presence). The NFVI is made up of three basic components: the hardware resources, the virtualisation layer, and the virtual resources. Such virtual resources can be either virtual machines (hypervisor-based virtualisation) or containers (container-based virtualisation).

Virtual Network Functions (VNFs): virtualisations of network functions (NFs) from a legacy, non-virtualised network. Examples of NFs are routers, switches and firewalls. VNFs are intended for deployment on commodity hardware.

NFV Management and Orchestration (NFV-MANO): architectural framework managing the NFVI and orchestrating the allocation of resources needed by the Network Services (NSs) and the VNFs. NFV-MANO is composed of three main functional blocks:

- **Virtualised Infrastructure Manager (VIM):** responsible for controlling and managing the NFVI computational, storage and network resources.
- **VNF Manager (VNFM):** responsible for the lifecycle management of VNF instances.
- **NFV Orchestrator (NFVO):** responsible for the orchestration of NFVI resources across multiple VIMs and for the lifecycle management of Network Services.

Finally, the Operating/Business Support System (OSS/BSS) represents other operators’ operations not explicitly captured in the current architectural framework. However, OSS/BSS is expected to exchange information with the functional blocks of the NFV-MANO architectural framework.

III. TAILORING ETSI NFV ARCHITECTURE FOR NTN

To address the integration of NTN and align them with the ETSI NFV architectural framework, the employment of a massive constellation of interconnected satellites, working as a single cluster should be assumed. This dynamic network comprises satellites acting as mobile nodes offering computing, storage, memory, and networking resources. A reasonable implementation of the framework incorporates the

satellite cluster on the NFVI block of the ETSI framework and utilises Open Source MANO (OSM) and Kubernetes for NFV-MANO. OSM would be in charge of handling the efficient deployment of VNFs on satellites within the cluster, managing the resource allocation, and ensuring workload health and availability. Kubernetes would act as the VIM, managing container scheduling, load balancing, fault tolerance, and addressing connectivity disruptions arising from satellite movements. Satellites within this framework can deploy container-based VNFs, allowing the instantiation of application images for service provision. Figure 2 shows the proposed NFV-MANO implementation.

Fig. 2. NFV-MANO framework implementation

IV. METHODOLOGY

The first step to assess the security risks endangering NFV-MANO is identifying the related threats. Being their number potentially elevated, it is convenient to split them in groups or categories. Microsoft’s STRIDE [7] is a well-known threat model, whose approach to identify security flaws contemplates the use of six threat categories: Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information disclosure, Denial of service, and Elevation of privilege.

STRIDE has been already used in the past to establish the security posture of telecommunication systems (e.g., to analyse software-defined networks [8], or to build a threat taxonomy for virtualised 5G networks [9]) and, more in general, of cyber-physical systems [10]. STRIDE’s threat-based approach well suits situations where the system under analysis is in rapid evolution in terms of design and configuration. Furthermore, given its generality, STRIDE is also indicated when analysing systems from a high-level architectural standpoint, especially in conjunction with a suitable vulnerability scoring system (such as CVSS, described further in this section).

To apply STRIDE, one follows four phases: 1) decomposition of the system into security-relevant components; 2) representation of the system and its components as a *data flow diagram* (DFD); 3) analysis of each component in the DFD for susceptibility to the STRIDE threat categories; 4) mitigation

of the threats. The process can be iterated until all the risks related to the mitigated threats are deemed acceptable.

DFDs are a graphical notation which models the interactions in an information system using four element types: *a*) processes, i.e., computations or programs; *b*) data stores, i.e., databases, files or logs; *c*) external interactors, i.e., end points of the system; *d*) data flows, i.e., communication data. To these, STRIDE introduces a fifth element, the trust boundary, used to isolate trustworthy and untrustworthy elements.

Threat modeling with STRIDE can be conducted in two possible ways: “per element”, or “per interaction”. The former, as it considers the behaviour of each system component, is more time-consuming, and can have a higher rate of false positives; the latter (which is chosen in the present work) is more focused on the interaction, revealing the most critical aspects of the system, and its results are usually sufficient to guarantee a good protection, as cyber-attacks normally involve malicious interactions between system components.

Once the threats connected with the system elements (or with the interactions between them) are highlighted, one can derive the correspondent vulnerabilities, and assess their severity to prioritise the search for mitigation. Suitable methods for vulnerability scoring are, for instance, the Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) by the Forum of Incident Response and Security Teams (FIRST) [11], and the DREAD risk assessment model by Microsoft. In this article, CVSS is preferred, due to its versatility and its large usage among the security community. The choice of CVSS is also justified by its ability to encompass, with its comprehensive set of metrics, the scoring of vulnerabilities affecting both TNs and NTN.

ETSI [12] proposes an asset-based methodology (derived from ISO 15408) for the analysis of the threats to NFV-MANO (and more in general, to the NFV model itself), and presents lists of assets, threats, threat agents, along with security objectives. ETSI’s analysis, anyhow, fails to stress the relationship between the threats and the different components of the NFV-MANO reference architecture, and presents very general and abstract findings, being the listed threats as a matter of fact genuine categories of threats (“manipulation”, “repudiation”, “denial of service”). One contribution of the present work is going further in the analysis to cover ETSI’s gaps, systematically characterising the different threats, as well as investigating their relationship with the several parts composing the unified orchestrator, and with the main external functional blocks communicating with it.

V. SECURITY ASSESSMENT

A. NFV Data Flow Diagram

The first step of the STRIDE analysis is the creation of a Data Flow Diagram (DFD) (Fig. 3). Here, the NFVO and the VNFM functional blocks are represented as a single process, as supported by the generic VNFM concept [13].

Indeed, when analysing the Or-Vnfm interaction (“reference point”), the VNF lifecycle management interface exposed by VNFM and the interfaces offered by NFVO (VNF package, granting, and resource management) are mutually dependent.

Fig. 3. NFV data flow diagram

This co-dependency is handled more comfortably when these interfaces are integrated in a single application/process, while it is more difficult to achieve when the implementations come from different vendors/suppliers. Congruently, implementing NFVO and VNFM within the same framework ensures compliance with industry standards, fostering interoperability and compatibility with third-party solutions. This reasoning is supported by the vast majority of NFV-MANO implementations, e.g., OSM [14] and ONAP [15].

Continuing with the analysis of the DFD, it can be observed that, although the VIM is included in the NFV-MANO framework (Fig. 1), ETSI states that its implementation is outside the scope of NFV-MANO. Because of this, the VIM is considered an external interactor which interfaces with NFVO/VNFM, following an architectural option (envisioned by ETSI [13]) in which the VNF resource management is done by NFVO (NFVO/VNFM in this case) via the Or-Vi interface. Regarding the NFVI functional block, since it does not interface directly with NFVO/VNFM, it can be modeled alongside the VIM as an external interactor.

Concerning the VNF and EM functional blocks, ETSI [13] foresees an architectural option where EM can be deployed, at VNF instantiation time, as an embedded part of VNF. Moreover, as previously stated in Section IV, the selected methodology for the threat modeling is the “per interaction” variant of STRIDE. Hence, to avoid duplication of threats (having the two reference points Ve-Vnfm-em and Ve-Vnfm-vnf almost the same interactions with the main orchestration process), and considered the aforementioned architectural option, we decided to merge VNF and EM in a single block. The Ve-Vnfm-vnf reference point is selected to be the interface with the main orchestration process. Finally, the facts that NFVI is considered an external interactor and that both VNFs and EMs are deployed in that infrastructure, allows us to consider VNF/EM an external interactor too.

Regarding OSS/BSS, its interface with the main orchestration process represents the integration with legacy systems of one or more operators’ networks. As the implementation of

TABLE I
THREAT ANALYSIS OUTPUT

Id	Description	Segment	Interactions	Score	CVSS string
1	Any external entity (functional block) may be spoofed by an attacker and this may lead to data being sent to the attacker's target instead of any external interactor. The satellite segment case resulted to be more sensitive than the ground segment, by considering both the wider attack surface and the lower attack complexity [17]. (Spoofing)	Ground	1, 2, 3	7.3	av:a/ac:h/pr:h/ui:n/s:c/c:h/i:n/a:h
		Satellite	1, 2	7.5	av:n/ac:l/pr:n/ui:n/s:c/c:n/i:n/a:h
2	VNF/NS or NFV/NFVI data stores, may be spoofed by an attacker. This may lead to incorrect data delivered to NFVO/VNFM, as data being written to the attacker's target. (Spoofing)	Ground	4, 5	7.6	av:a/ac:h/pr:h/ui:n/s:c/c:h/i:h/a:h
3	Authenticated data flow compromised. An attacker can read or modify data transmitted over an authenticated data flow. For the ground segment interfaces Or-Vi, Ve-Vnfm-vnf and Os-Ma-nfvo are considered. Regarding the satellite segment, only Or-Vi, Ve-Vnfm-vnf interfaces are considered. (Tampering)	Ground	1, 2, 3	7.6	av:a/ac:h/pr:h/ui:n/s:c/c/h/i:h/a:h
		Satellite	1, 2	7.9	av:n/ac:h/pr:h/ui:n/s:c/c/h/i:h/a:l
4	Potential SQL injection vulnerability for VNF/NS or NFV Ins/NFVI data stores. Malicious code inserted into strings, passed to an SQL instance for parsing and execution. (Tampering)	Ground	4, 5	7.5	av:a/ac:h/pr:h/ui:n/s:c/c/i:h/a:h
5	NFVO/VNFM claims that it did not receive data from a source outside the trust boundary. (Repudiation)	Ground	1, 2, 3	3.0	av:l/ac:h/pr:h/ui:n/s:c/c:l/i:l/a:n
6	VIM/NFVI, VNF/EM or OSS/BSS claims that it did not receive data from a process on the other side of the trust boundary. (Repudiation)	Ground, Satellite	1, 2, 3	3.0	av:l/ac:h/pr:h/ui:n/s:c/c/l/i:l/a:n
7	Authorisation bypass. Possibility to access VNF/NS or NFV Ins/NFVI data stores directly and bypass the NFVO/VNFM, by having parallel access to both data stores. (Inf. Disclosure)	Ground	4, 5	5.3	av:l/ac:h/pr:h/ui:n/s:c/c/h/i:n/a:n
8	Resource weak access control. Improper data protection of VNF/NS or NFV Ins/NFVI data stores, can allow an attacker to read information not intended for disclosure. (Inf. Disclosure)	Ground	4, 5	5.3	av:l/ac:h/pr:h/ui:n/s:c/c/h/i:n/a:n
9	Any of NFVO/VNFM, VIM/NFVI or OSS/BSS crashes, halts, stops or runs slowly; in all cases violating an availability metric. (Denial of Service)	Ground, Satellite	1, 2, 3	5.4	av:a/ac:h/pr:h/ui:n/s:c/c/n/i:n/a:h
10	Data flow Or-Vi, Ve-Vnfm-vnf or Os-Ma-nfvo is potentially interrupted. An external agent interrupts data flowing across a trust boundary in either direction. For the ground segment interfaces Or-Vi, Ve-Vnfm-vnf and Os-Ma-nfvo are considered. Regarding the satellite segment, only Or-Vi, Ve-Vnfm-vnf interfaces are considered. (Denial of Service)	Ground	1, 2, 3	6.8	av:n/ac:h/pr:n/ui:n/s:c/c/n/i:n/a:h
		Satellite	1, 2	5.8	av:n/ac:l/pr:n/ui:n/s:c/c/n/i:n/a:l
11	Potential excessive resource consumption for NFVO/VNFM or any data store connected to him, VNF/NS or NFV Ins/NFVI Resources. (Denial of Service)	Ground, Satellite	4, 5	6.2	av:a/ac:l/pr:h/ui:n/s:c/c/n/i:n/a:h
12	NFVO/VNFM, OSS/BSS, VIM/NFVI or VNF/EM, may be subject to Elevation of Privilege using remote code execution. (Elevation of Privilege)	Ground, Satellite	1, 2, 3	7.3	av:a/ac:h/pr:h/ui:n/s:c/c/n/i:n/a:h
13	Elevation by changing the execution flow in NFVO/VNFM, OSS/BSS or VIM/NFVI. (Elevation of Privilege)	Ground, Satellite	1, 2, 3	7.3	av:a/ac:h/pr:h/ui:n/s:c/c/n/i:h/a:h
14	Cross-site request forgery (CSRF or XSRF) against vulnerable APIs/UI of NFVO/VNFM, OSS/BSS or VIM/NFVI (ground segment VIM). (Elevation of Privilege)	Ground	1, 3	6.2	av:n/ac:h/pr:h/ui:r/s:c/c/n/i:h/a:l

Interaction references: Or-Vi (1), Ve-Vnfm-vnf (2), Os-Ma-nfvo (3), Or-vnf-db (4), Or-nfvi-db (5)

such systems are completely outside the NFV scope, they are considered as external interactors in the DFD.

Finally, OSS/BSS and NFVO/VNFM are thought to be instantiated in the ground segment, while VIM/NFVI and VNF/EM in the ground and satellite segment.

B. CVSS scoring

As previously mentioned, in this work threats are evaluated using the Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS), in its version 3.1. The system is the *de facto* standard for the scoring of vulnerabilities/threats in the information security field, and contemplates the assessment along eight axes: Attack Vector (AV), Attack Complexity (AC), Privileges Required (PR), User Interaction (UI), Scope (S), Confidentiality (C), Integrity (I), Availability (A).

Using the acronyms for the axes and their values, a CVSS assessment can be written in a succinct form as a single string.

As an example, the string

AV:A/AC:H/PR:L/UI:N/S:C/C:H/I:H/A:H

would represent a score with Attack Vector equal to Adjacent, Attack Complexity equal to High, and so on. To each combination of values, a final numerical score between zero (no threat) and ten (maximum threat) is attributed.

C. Threats analysis and results

This section captures the threat analysis and its results. A total of 43 threats have been obtained as a result of the first analysis. Subsequently, we meticulously examined each threat, taking into account similarities in scenario descriptions, categories, and common interface usage, leading to the categorization of threats into distinct groups. This grouping process yielded a final selection of 14 threats. Finally, each threat was assessed using CVSS to derive its numerical score. The resulting cases are presented in Table I. Each case includes, the segment(s) affected, the interface(s) involved in the case interaction(s), the CVSS score and string.

Hereinafter, only the threats with score equal to or greater than 7 are thoroughly analysed; the remaining ones are captured in Table I and not treated any further. When applicable, dedicated scores have been assessed for the ground (TN) and satellite (NTN) segments, to highlight their differences from the security standpoint. Moreover, we considered standard security protocols for both segments' interfaces when performing the CVSS scoring as the minimal set required by the industry, when designing an architecture that handles sensitive data. Ground segment interfaces Or-Vi, Ve-Vnfm-vnf, and Os-Ma-nfvo were assumed to implement TLS and L2TP/IPsec, while

data store interfaces were thought to have authentication and encryption in place. TLS guarantees authentication, integrity, and confidentiality. L2TP/IPsec is in place for securing the communication between OSM and the satellite operator network. For satellite segment interfaces Ve-Vnfm-vnf and Or-Vi, protocols like Encapsulation Packet Protocol (EPP), Space Data Link Security Protocol (SDL-SP), and IP over CCSDS Space Links (IPoC) from CCSDS [16] were assumed in place. One key aspect about IPoC is that it allows the integration of terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks, by enabling end-to-end routing of IP datagrams over space data links.

Starting with threat Id 1, by spoofing VIM/NFVI or VNF/EM in the ground segment, it can be considered a scenario where the commands sent by NFVO/VNFM to increase the resources of a particular NS are disregarded. This will affect the quality of service and availability of that particular NS, but this can easily be scaled to all NSs deployed in this VIM/NFVI, affecting a larger part of the operation (high impact on availability). By spoofing OSS/BSS, the attacker can obtain information about the entirety of the NS catalogue deployed and managed by the NFVO/VNFM. With this knowledge, the attacker can affect the functionalities of the NSs (bypassing the authorisation controls), or upload a malicious VNF package to perform DoS attacks from inside the NS architecture perimeter (high impact on availability). Finally, for the satellite segment case, the spoofing of a satellite service, e.g., GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System), could potentially affect the whole satellite cluster [17] with severe impact on its availability.

Considering the case of threat Id 2, by spoofing any of the data stores (VNF/NS Catalogue or NFV Inst / NFVI Res), both confidentiality and integrity would be highly compromised. This would lead to information disclosure of the NSs deployed, of the infrastructure resources, and of their state and configuration. At the same time, a malicious VNF could be delivered and deployed into the infrastructure to alter the data flow or even to perform a DoS attack inside the infrastructure, with an even higher impact on the availability.

In the case of threat Id 3, an authenticated data flow (Or-Vi, Ve-Vnfm-vnf or Os-Ma-nfvo) between an external interactor and NFVO/VNFM is compromised by an attacker able to exploit a vulnerability in the communication protocol stack. The attacker can then read or modify the transmitted data. In a concrete case, this attack would require bypassing the secure communication measures in place, namely TLS and IPsec for the ground segment and SDL-SP for the satellite segment, and it is thus considered of high complexity. On the other hand, a successful compromise of such a communication channel would most likely result in a severe leakage of (possibly sensitive) data, along with possible manipulation of the communication flow, and even a complete functional incapacitation of the network. The impacts on the attributes of confidentiality, availability and integrity are thus rated as “high”, which leads to the final score of 7.6/10. For the satellite segment, the score is 7.9/10, the slight increment due to the existence of a wider attack vector in this case [18], because

there is no need to be connected to the satellite operator’s network.

Threat Id 4 addresses possible SQL injections from NFVO/VNFM to the VNF/NS Catalogue and NFV Instances / NFVI Resources databases, and hence it applies to the ground segment only. The attack is evaluated considering that high user privileges are required to access any provided interface of the NFVO/VNFM (namely, REST API or Web UI); differently from the previous cases, the impact on confidentiality is assessed as less important.

In the case of threat Id 12, a vulnerability (e.g., in the Linux kernel) is exploited by a (possibly internal) attacker to escalate their privileges in the system and execute code remotely. Example of remote code execution are buffer overflow vulnerabilities, deserialisation vulnerabilities, memory corruptions, as exposed in [18], for the satellite segment. This attack is considered executable from an adjacent network and, having a high impacts on integrity and confidentiality, is assessed with a score of 7.3/10.

Finally, threat Id 13 presents the scenario of a malicious change of execution flow. An attacker could pass forged data into any of the mentioned functional blocks, and be able to change the flow of program execution. An example of this case is also presented in [18] for the satellite segment. Nevertheless, the necessity for the attacker to operate inside the NFV virtual network (like in most previous cases) leads to a score of 7.3/10.

VI. SECURITY OBJECTIVES

Following the identification and description of security threats targeting the NFV-MANO architecture, this section establishes a set of security objectives. These objectives essentially represent countermeasures designed to mitigate the identified attacks. Additionally, we provide practical guidelines for implementing these security objectives.

Table II analyses the aforementioned security objectives and demonstrates their feasibility within a realistic NFV-MANO implementation where the NFVO/VNFM components are devised by using the OSM reference implementation by ETSI, and the VIM function is taken into account by the well-known container orchestration tool Kubernetes (additional details in Section III). Particularly, Table II provides a comprehensive analysis of the security objectives. It not only details their objectives but also offers supplementary recommendations for implementation. Additionally, the table establishes correspondences between these objectives, the OSM-Kubernetes architecture, and the relevant threats identified in Table I.

As a result, this work both verifies the efficacy of the proposed security objectives in a practical scenario and offers concrete technical guidance for securing NFV-MANO deployments.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

In this article, we have considered a general model of a unified orchestrator for terrestrial and non-terrestrial virtualised networks, leveraged a well-known threat analysis framework

TABLE II
SECURITY OBJECTIVES FOR TERRESTRIAL AND NON-TERRESTRIAL RESOURCES

Security Objective	Recommendations	Implementation	Threat
The system should provide authentication, authorisation, integrity and confidentiality of data exchanged over interfaces. (1)	Implement Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) for authentication/authorisation. Make use of TLS, IPsec and/or SSH to provide confidentiality and integrity for data in transit.	OSM implements Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) and TLS (HTTPS) or SSH to secure its communication interfaces. Kubernetes supports ABAC and can be integrated with LDAP/OAuth.	1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 12, 13, 14
The system should ensure that repudiation is mitigated. (2)	Implement secure logging, by providing integrity protection for locally stored log entries, and being able to send them to a remote location. Encrypt log entries both in transit and at rest.	OSM implements audit logs and can export them to external systems. Kubernetes provides tamper-evident logs, as well as management solutions to store and monitor audit logs.	5, 6
The system should detect and mitigate DoS attacks over the different architecture exposed interfaces. (3)	Implement one or more of the following proposed measures: attack detection, allow/deny specific IP and physical (MAC) addresses, rate limiting.	Set a firewall as a VNF (managed by the NFVO/VNFM) to allow/deny IP addresses. Under heavy attack conditions NFVO/VNFM can scale up adding more resource instances.	10
The system should detect and mitigate excessive resources consumption. (4)	Implement OS-level access and confinement controls (e.g., SELinux, sVirt). Limit resource consumption for containerised VNFs.	Kubernetes provides resource quotas and limit ranges to limit resource consumption. Furthermore, it can assign SELinux labels to containers.	9, 11, 12
The system should detect and mitigate manipulation attacks. (5)	Apply integrity check functions (cryptographic hash function generating a fixed-length output from an input of arbitrary length) to immutable elements of code, data or container images.	OSM performs integrity checks on the on-boarded VNF packages (vendor signature). Kubernetes verifies image signatures via admission control. Data exchange between OSM and Kubernetes is signed.	3, 12, 13
The system should ensure the availability of data to be provided over the interfaces. (6)	Implement high availability for critical applications. Deploy more than one NFVI-PoP for the ground segment infrastructure. Scale up resources for the satellite segment when needed.	OSM can be deployed in HA mode, on a private (on-premises) and public (AWS, GCP, etc.) cloud. Kubernetes adds rapid resource orchestration for the satellite segment when needed.	9, 10

to discover the possible threats associated with the model, conducted a detailed analysis and a quantitative scoring of the severity of the discovered threats, distinguishing the terrestrial from the non-terrestrial (satellite) cases, and finally proposed a set of security measures apt to mitigate the most conspicuous threats, mapping such measures onto a specific instance of the general NFV-MANO model, i.e., using the OSM / Kubernetes reference implementation.

Our contribution is part of an ongoing work that takes the set of security objectives as an input for setting an experimental implementation, in a laboratory environment, of the security measures. Further supporting material, outcome of this work, is available online [19].

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the Spanish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation and the European Union – NextGeneration EU, in the framework of the Recovery Plan, Transformation and Resilience (PRTR) (Call UNICO I+D 5G 2021, ref. number TSI-063000-2021-1-6GSatNet-GS).

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Araniti, A. Iera, S. Pizzi and F. Rinaldi, "Toward 6G Non-Terrestrial Networks," *IEEE Network*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 113–120, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1109/MNET.011.2100191.
- [2] A. Bajpai and A. Balodi, "Role of 6G Networks: Use Cases and Research Directions," in 2020 IEEE Bangalore Humanitarian Technology Conference (B-HTC), Oct. 2020, pp. 1–5. doi: 10.1109/B-HTC50970.2020.9298017.
- [3] A. Ghosh, A. Maeder, M. Baker and D. Chandramouli, "5G Evolution: A View on 5G Cellular Technology Beyond 3GPP Release 15," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 127639–127651, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2939938.
- [4] M. Pattaranantakul, R. He, Q. Song, Z. Zhang and A. Meddahi, "NFV security survey: from use case driven threat analysis to state-of-the-art countermeasures," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 20, no. 4, July 2018.

- [5] A. Roy-Chowdhury, J. S. Baras, M. Hadjitheodosiou and S. Papademetriou, "Security issues in hybrid networks with a satellite component," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 50–61, Dec. 2005, doi: 10.1109/MWC.2005.1561945.
- [6] ETSI GS NFV 002, "Network Functions Virtualization (NFV); Architectural Framework," December 2014.
- [7] L. Kohnfelder and P. Garg, "The threats to our products," *Microsoft Interface*, April 1999.
- [8] F. Ruffy, W. Hommel and F. von Eye, "A STRIDE-based security architecture for software-defined networking," *Fifteenth Int. Conf. on Networks*, 2016.
- [9] T. Madi, H. Alameddine, M. Pourzandi and A. Boukhtouta, "NFV security survey in 5G networks: A three-dimensional threat taxonomy," *Computer Networks*, vol. 197, issue C, October 2021.
- [10] R. Khan, K. McLaughlin, D. Lavery and S. Sezer, "STRIDE-based threat modeling for cyber-physical systems," 2017 IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Conference Europe (ISGT-Europe), Turin, 2017, pp. 1–6.
- [11] Online. Retrieved on 2024-02-12, <https://www.first.org/cvss/>.
- [12] "TS 102 165-1 - CYBER; Methods and protocols; Part 1: Method and pro forma for Threat, Vulnerability, Risk Analysis (TVRA)," version 5.2.5, ETSI, Jan. 2022.
- [13] ETSI GS NFV-IFA 009, "Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV); Management and Orchestration; Report on Architectural Options," July 2016.
- [14] ETSI, "Open Source MANO," Accessed 2024-02-09. [Online]. Available: <https://osm.etsi.org/>.
- [15] L. Foundation, "ONAP–Open Network Automation Platform," Accessed 2024-02-09. [Online]. Available: <https://www.onap.org/>.
- [16] CCSDS, "Overview of space communications protocols," Consultative Committee for Space Data System, Report, 2023. Accessed 2024-02-09. [Online]. Available: <https://public.ccsds.org/Pubs/130x0g4e1.pdf>.
- [17] P. Tedeschi, S. Sciancalepore, R. Di Pietro, "Satellite-based communications security: A survey of threats, solutions, and research challenges," *Computer Networks*, vol. 216, October 2022.
- [18] J. Willbold, M. Schloegel, M. Voegelé, M. Gerhardt, T. Holz, A. Abbasi, "Space Odyssey: an experimental software security analysis of satellites," 2023, IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy, San Francisco, USA.
- [19] M. Battaglia, J. M. Villarreal D'Angelo, "Threat analysis material for unified network orchestrator across terrestrial and non-terrestrial resources," 2024, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10908586. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/10908586>.